

Stability and recrystallization of amorphous solid dispersions prepared by hot-melt extrusion and spray drying

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ABSTRACT

Spray drying and hot-melt extrusion are among the most prevalent preparation techniques used in the pharmaceutical industry to produce amorphous solid dispersions (ASDs). This study advances previous research by integrating sample production, comprehensive analytical characterization, intrinsic dissolution rate measurements, and assessments of the behavior of ASDs under elevated temperature and humidity conditions. The study focuses on indomethacin, a widely used model for poorly soluble drugs, processed with PVP K30 or HPMC E5, both commonly used polymers. The findings demonstrate that hot-melt extruded samples exhibit superior stability against recrystallization, whereas spray dried samples achieve higher intrinsic dissolution rates. Furthermore, PVP K30 significantly outperforms HPMC E5 in the co-processing of indomethacin, enhancing both the intrinsic dissolution rate and the stability.

1. Introduction

The low aqueous solubility of drugs is a significant challenge in the pharmaceutical industry as it leads to low bioavailability of drugs. Solubility is defined as the amount of a solid drug that dissolves in a given volume of solvent under specific conditions, often chosen to mimic the gastrointestinal tract. Bioavailability refers to the fraction of the drug that enters the systemic circulation in its unchanged form after administration (Olivares-Morales, 2014). Limited dissolution can reduce bioavailability by limiting absorption through the intestinal wall into the bloodstream. In addition, the amount absorbed is influenced by the excretion or metabolism via first-pass metabolism (Bhalani, 2022).

To correlate bioavailability with measurable characteristics, the biopharmaceutics classification system (BCS) was developed, which categorizes drugs into a 2x2 matrix based on their solubility and permeability (Amidon, 1995). Low bioavailability necessitates higher doses, which can lead to more pronounced adverse effects, increased drug manufacturing costs, and significant amounts of the drug being excreted without therapeutic effect, contributing to wastewater pollution and erratic absorption (Bhalani, 2022; Atal and Bedi, 2010; Kawabata, 2011; Ortúzar, 2022). Currently, a high proportion of marketed drugs and most drugs in the research pipeline suffer from low

solubility (Loftsson and Brewster, 2010), and this trend is expected to continue.

Various approaches are used to address low solubility, some of which are shown in Table SI 1. One method is formulating drugs into amorphous solid forms, which enhances dissolution by reducing the energy required to release drug molecules into the solvent. However, a common drawback of amorphous drug products is decreased physical stability, leading to a transformation into a more thermodynamically stable crystalline form (Bhugra and Pikal, 2008). To mitigate this, amorphous drugs are typically formulated with polymers that stabilize dispersion through weak forces or steric barriers (Knopp, 2015). Another advantage of amorphous solid dispersion drug products is improved wetting due to the hydrophilic nature of many polymers (Sareen et al., 2012), further enhancing dissolution. Polymers also stabilize the dissolved drug in a supersaturated state.

The inherent decreased stability of ASDs, leading to recrystallization, is a critical focus in formulation. Unlike crystalline drugs, ASDs lack long-range molecular order, which explains their higher dissolution rates. However, lower stability drives the system towards a more stable composition, which can cause recrystallization or phase separation (Shi, 2020). This is undesirable, as it negates the benefits of the amorphous form (Sun, 2012) and introduces uncertainty in the crystalline drug

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fraction, posing risks to patients. Stability tests are essential to identify potential product degradation, typically conducted under elevated temperature and humidity conditions, which are the primary factors in drug degradation and recrystallization.

There are two primary methods for producing ASDs. The first involves heating a drug-polymer mixture until it becomes a liquid (a melt) and then rapidly cooling it to lock the dispersed molecules in place. The second method dissolves a mixture of the drug and a suitable stabilizer in a volatile solvent, which is then quickly evaporated. These methods can be performed using simple techniques, such as hot-melt quenching or rotary evaporation on a laboratory scale, which is useful during the screening phase. However, these techniques can be unreliable when scaled up. More controlled manufacturing processes that facilitate easier scale-up include hot-melt extrusion (HME, heat processing) (Sekiguchi and Obi, 1961) and spray drying (SD, solvent evaporation) (Tachibana and Nakamura, 1965). Both HME and SD can be conducted continuously, reducing batch variability, minimizing equipment downtime, and improving process control. These preparation methods have already been used to produce commercial products, demonstrating their potential for new drug development. A list of some commercial products is shown in Table SI 2.

Although SD and HME have been used for the production of ASDs, there is no comparison of the ASD prepared by both above-mentioned methods in terms of their long-term stability and behavior during dissolution. Therefore, we will compare these production methods using indomethacin, a nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug with low solubility and high permeability, making it a class 2 drug according to the BCS classification (Xi, 2020). This study will be conducted using two industrially relevant polymers, PVP K30 and HPMC E5, to facilitate the dissolution of amorphous indomethacin. Given the poor solubility of the drug, we will use high drug loading at the limit of drug/polymer compatibility, as suggested by the literature (Chaudhari and Dave, 2016). This approach allows us to avoid unnecessarily increasing the viscosity of the mixture, which could slow down the dissolution (Li, 2019).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

γ -indomethacin (TCI chemicals, Belgium), PVP K30 (OrionPharma, Finland), HPMC E5 (OrionPharma, Finland), ethanol (absolute for UV, min 99.8 %, Penta Chemicals, Czechia), DMSO (min. 99 %, Lach-ner, Czechia) and demineralized water were used in this study.

2.2. Spray drying

Buchi B290 with an inert loop B295 was used for all spray drying experiments. Indomethacin:polymer at composition 70:30 w/w was prepared by dissolving 3 g of the solids mixture in 200 ml of ethanol with optionally 50 ml of water (Ind:HPMC product, to allow molecular dissolution of HPMC) (Chaudhari and Dave, 2016).

The conditions used for the drying experiment were 90 °C inlet temperature, 100 % aspirator flow rate (35 m³/h), 50 mm atomizer rate (601 l/h), 30 % feed flow rate (8.2 ml/min). They were selected in the manner of Mueller et al. (Mueller, 2023). The produced particles were dried under vacuum overnight without being heated.

2.3. Hot-melt extrusion

The same composition of indomethacin:polymer was selected, 70:30 w/w. Polymers used are PVP K30 and HPMC E5. The extrusion was carried out in the Three Tec ZE5 twin screw extruder with 4 heating zones, 3 mm die and 40:1 L:D ratio. The feeding zone was cooled with tap water so as not to melt the powder prematurely to allow continuous feeding.

The extrusion conditions used for the Ind:PVP sample were 50 rpm, 110/130/150/150 °C (Chokshi, 2005); for the Ind:HPMC sample, they were 50 rpm, 110/150/170/175 °C based on our condition screening to allow complete amorphization of the product. The powder feed rate was set to 2.5 % on the ZD 5 FB i6000 feeder by Three Tec, which is equal to mass flow rate of 0.1044 g/min.

Filaments produced using HME were milled using a mortar and a pestle prior to analysis using DSC and XRPD and other processing.

2.4. Characterization of the products

X-ray diffraction was carried out using XRPD (Bruker) in reflective mode in Bragg-Brentano geometry with a CuK α anode with an emitted wavelength of 1.542 Å at 40 kV and 40 mA and equipped with a LYNXEYE_XE_T detector in 1D mode. Sample powder was pressed onto a flat surface on a plastic holder, placed on a stand, and then measured using the instrument arm automatically. The measurement was carried out between the measurement angles 2–40 of $^{\circ}2\theta$ with a step size of 0.02 of $^{\circ}2\theta$.

The TGAs were performed on a Pyris 6 TGA (Perkin Elmer). The samples were weighed in ceramic pans and measured in nitrogen flow. TGA investigations were performed in a temperature range of 20 °C to 250 °C with a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The weight sample was about 19–22 mg.

Differential scanning calorimetry measurements were performed by enclosing 2–5 mg of sample powder inside an aluminum measurement pan (TA Instruments) and then placing it inside the measurement carousel of the Discovery DSC (TA Instruments) using a temperature range of 20–200 °C with a 5 °C/min heating rate and a modulation of 0.8 °C with a 60 s period. Data analysis was carried out using the TRIOS software (TA Instruments) by deconvolution of the signal into total, reversing, and nonreversing heat flows. T_g was selected as the midpoint of the reversible heat flow step, and the enthalpy of melting was evaluated by integrating the total heat flow peak around the melting temperature of γ indometacin polymorph.

Infrared spectra were captured using the iS50 FT-IR (Nicolet), where the background spectrum was measured, followed by stabilization of the powder sample between the diamond glass window and the sample holder. The spectra were captured between 4000 and 400 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. 64 readings of the spectra were averaged for a final spectrum result of each sample, as well as the background.

Solid state NMR spectra were obtained using the 400 WB (Bruker) in the 13C cross-polarized magic angle spinning configuration with 4 mm rotor at 13 kHz spinning speed. The analysis and visualization were carried out in TopSpin software.

Dynamic vapor sorption (DVS) data were obtained using DVS Adventure (SMS) using an experiment at 25 °C with a 10 % RH step from 0-90 % RH with two consecutive runs to evaluate the water sorption behaviour of the produced samples at different humidity conditions.

The intrinsic dissolution rate was evaluated using the InForm machine (Pion) from an 8 mm in diameter IDR disc in 40 ml of PBS buffer with 6.8 pH at 100 rpm and 37 °C for 1 h. Concentration measurement was carried out using a UV spectrophotometer with a calibration curve prepared in the concentration range by dissolving known amounts of indomethacin in DMSO and adding known volumes to the PBS buffer. The evaluation was carried out between 300 and 350 nm with a simple correction for scattered light.

The size and shape evaluation for the spray dried powders was carried out using SEM (Tescan CLARA) by adding powder to an aluminum stub covered with carbon tape and gold sputtering, and the conditions of image acquisition are shown in the SEM image. The size and shape evaluation for the hot-melt extruded filament and powder was carried out using an optical microscope (Olympus DSX1000). EDS result was obtained using the Ultim Max 65 (Oxford Instruments, UK) at voltage 15 kV and 2000x magnification, focusing on chlorine atoms detection.

Crystallinity characterization using DSC was carried out by

comparing the melting enthalpy of γ -indometacin (106 J/g (Atef, 2012)) with the melting enthalpy of the measured sample and adjusting to the drug load (70 %), as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\text{crystallinity} = \frac{\Delta H_{\text{melting}}(\text{measured sample})}{\Delta H_{\text{melting}}(\gamma\text{Indometacin}) \bullet \text{drugload}} \quad (1)$$

Comparison of the T_g values of prepared ASDs with the value expected by ideal mixing of two substances was carried out. The T_g as expected from the ideal mixing was calculated using the Gordon-Taylor equation. According to the Gordon-Taylor equation (Gordon and Taylor, 1952), the T_g of the two-component mixture depends on the mass fractions of components A (in this work the drug) and B (the polymer), x_A and x_B , respectively, the glass transition temperatures of pure substances A and B denoted as $T_{g,A}^0$ and $T_{g,B}^0$, and the densities of components A and B, defined as ρ_A^0 and ρ_B^0 .

$$T_g = \frac{x_A T_{g,A}^0 + K x_B T_{g,B}^0}{x_A + K x_B} \quad (2)$$

$$K = \frac{T_{g,A}^0 \rho_A^0}{T_{g,B}^0 \rho_B^0} \quad (3)$$

For the stress test, the samples were placed in an open vial at 60 °C and 75 % RH. Samples were taken on day 5. The aim was to see recrystallization and a change in the behaviour of the sample.

The stability test was carried out under conditions 30 or 40 °C and 11 or 75 % RH. The samples were taken at intervals 1; 3; 5; 7; 14 and 28 days. The aim was to see recrystallization kinetics, which was evaluated using mDSC by measuring the change in T_g and crystallinity of the sample (measured using the heat of melting).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Results of analyses of prepared ASD samples

As can be seen in Fig. 1, despite the high amount of API in the samples and considering the detection limit of XRD, the measurement shows that all the samples produced are fully amorphous without any traces of the crystalline forms of Indomethacin. To verify the XRD results, analysis using DSC was carried out for the samples, and the measured results are shown in Fig. 2 in the form of a reverse heat flow curve. The corresponding values of T_g , as well as the estimation of the amount of crystallinity in the samples, are shown in Table 1.

Apart from spray dried sample containing HPMC, the DSC measurement proved that there is only one T_g for all of the samples, confirming complete dissolution of indomethacin in the polymer without any phase separation. For samples with PVP, T_g occurs around 65 °C, while for HPMC, T_g is around 48–49 °C, close to the T_g value of pure amorphous indomethacin at 46 °C (Vyazovkin and Dranca, 2005). Such an increase

in T_g clearly confirms superior properties of PVP in stabilizing amorphous indomethacin compared to HPMC.

Furthermore, as shown in Table 1, the HPMC spray dried sample also has a small melting endotherm at 143.3 °C, which was evaluated compared to a fully crystalline indomethacin sample to signify approximately 0.7 % crystallinity using Eq. (1). Similar results have also been presented in the literature and this observation is attributed to the use of a high drug load (Chaudhari and Dave, 2016). This is below the XRPD detection limit, but leaves us to speculate about the reason for crystallinity, with the most probable reason being the application of a non-azeotropic solvent mixture, in which the ethanol phase was drug rich while the aqueous phase was HPMC rich. Under such conditions in the spray drying chamber, ethanol evaporated quickly compared to water and produced pure indomethacin regions, in which further recrystallization is possible. Thus, the problem would be phase separation, which is in agreement with Li et al. (Li, 2020), who also showed that in systems with high drug load and low secondary solvent concentration phase separation was visible by DSC, but not with other analytical methods. Compared to spray drying used in this article, higher inlet temperatures are sometimes used, however, this is often accompanied by a higher liquid flow rate (Chaudhari and Dave, 2016; Patterson, 2007). In our case, higher temperature has led to a more pronounced phase separation, while lower inlet temperatures have led to incomplete drying. Although spray drying starts in molecularly dissolved mixtures, due to non-azeotropic conditions could lead to a drug rich phase. In contrast, HME as a solvent-free process produces more homogeneous samples.

The empirical rule of “ $T_g - 50\text{ °C}$ ” (Yoshioka et al., 1994) states that for amorphous samples, if the glass transition temperature is more than 50 °C higher than the storage temperature, the sample should be safe against recrystallization due to the Arrhenius dependence of the recrystallization rate on temperature. On the other hand, recrystallization occurs faster, when the sample storage temperature is closer to the glass transition temperature. On the basis of our results, we can conclude that samples containing PVP are expected to be stable for extended periods of time even close to or at room temperature, whereas HPMC samples would need cooling to achieve prolonged stability.

The T_g calculated by the Gordon-Taylor equation (Eq. (2)) was compared with the measured T_g , as shown in Table 1, along with the type of deviation – positive for the PVP sample, negative for the HPMC sample. The deviations are due to the non-ideality of the component mixing, indicating what is the interaction between the components – whether the bonding will be stronger than the expected from ideal mixing (positive interaction) (Gupta, 2005), or weaker (negative interaction) (Shamblin et al., 1998).

Table 2 shows that there is some water adsorbed on all the samples, which is comparable for both techniques. This can be explained by the absorption of water vapor by the polymers used, which is most likely the equilibrium value. From the TGA result, all samples show good behaviour. This was also supported by low amount of adsorbed water obtained by DVS (see Fig. SI 1).

Fig. 1. XRPD plots of the produced samples, showing spray dried (blue), hot-melt extruded (red) products, and the starting crystalline material (black).

Fig. 2. Reversing heat flow of spray dried (blue) and hot-melt extruded (red) materials produced with either PVP (a) or HPMC (b).

Table 1

Glass transition temperature of the prepared samples with their melting enthalpy when occurring, together with the melting temperature [in brackets] and the calculated crystallinity. The T_g of amorphous indomethacin is approximately 46 °C (Vyazovkin and Dranca, 2005).

Sample	Measured T _g (°C)	ΔH _{melting} (J/g)	Crystallinity(%)	Calculated T _g (°C)	RD(%)	Interaction
Ind:PVP SD	65	0	0	53.9	20.1	Positive
Ind:PVP HME	65	0	0	53.9	20.5	Positive
Ind:HPMC SD	48	0.5 [143.3 °C]	0.7	51.5	6.0	Negative
Ind:HPMC HME	49	0	0	51.5	4.7	Negative

Table 2

Results of TGA and XRPD analyzes for the produced samples.

Sample	TGA result	XRPD result
PVP HME	1.1 % water	Fully amorphous
PVP SD	1.4 % water 0.1 % solvent	Fully amorphous
HPMC HME	1.2 % water	Fully amorphous
HPMC SD	0.9 % water	Fully amorphous

Solid-state NMR was performed for the starting material, e.g., γ indomethacin, PVP K30, HPMC E5, as well as samples produced by spray drying and hot-melt extrusion. By comparing the spectra shown in Fig. 3, it is seen that both peak shift and peak blend and broadening occurred for the samples, leading to products with different spectra, indicating amorphization, as explained by Lu et al. (Lu, 2019). The spectra produced from samples containing the same polymer with HME and SD are also strongly similar, indicating no thermal degradation of the samples. This is specifically important result for the HME HPMC sample, for which a higher temperature was used. On the other hand, no distinguishable differences have been found between the samples, similar to the analysis via XRPD.

As can be seen in Fig. 4, the spray dried materials were mainly spherical in shape with sizes around 2–5 μm , while the milled extrudates had a much broader size distribution from tens to hundreds of microns. For the spray dried materials, it is visible that the PVP sample is spherical in shape, owing to which we expect probably hollow spheres, as some dimpling is visible in larger particles. The HPMC sample clearly shows fibrous and spherical aggregates, where the fibers are most probably stemming from the polymer. To confirm this hypothesis, we performed the EDS analysis, focusing on chlorine atoms, as those are present in Indomethacin, while missing from HPMC E5. The combined image of SEM and EDS (see Fig. SI 2) confirmed missing chlorine atoms on the fibers. This behaviour could explain the poorer results from other analyses: some of the HPMC polymer has escaped being mixed with the API, as a result of which drug loading in the spherical particles rose, and the product is less stable. We can also see that the droplet breakup process is disturbed by those fibers, which led to collisions of semiwet particles and their subsequent binding. This is a clear indication that spray drying with HPMC leads to a lower-quality product.

For samples produced by hot-melt extrusion, there are fewer differences visible between the two polymers. Both lead to a macroscopic

filament, which is then milled and thus to the formation of a sharp, jagged appearance of the products. The milling also explains the wide-ness of the size distribution, as the process was not developed in a way to ensure a better size profile of the products and thus there are visible differences between various particle sizes. What can be seen from the images is that the Ind:PVP sample holds broken small particles on the surface of the bigger particles, probably mother particles, or the small particles are electrostatically bonded to the surface of the bigger particles. The surface becomes rougher as a result of presence of the small particles. On the other hand, the Ind:HPMC sample shows less of such bonding between particles of different sizes.

When optical microscope images of hot-melt extruded samples are taken, which are shown in Fig. SI 3, HPMC materials are slightly more jagged, most likely due to the material is harder to break with a mortar and a pestle. Fig. SI 2 also shows the small particles stuck to the surface of the larger particles, confirming what is visible on the SEM.

In summary, SEM images show that while spray drying leads to spherical particles with narrow size distribution, which are either separate (Ind:PVP case) or clumped together (Ind:HPMC case), hot-melt extrusion due to the necessity of subsequent milling leads to particles with broad size distribution and jagged shape. For this reason, as well as because of different sizes produced by the different methods, we have selected intrinsic dissolution rate measurement as the dissolution method that does not discriminate based on the particle size and shape due to disc production. The results of the IDR measurements are shown in the following section.

Further characterization was performed by measuring the IDR. A summary of the measured profiles is shown in Fig. 5. Due to nonlinear behaviour of the curves in the later time period of the dissolution, only points between 0 and 500 s were used to evaluate the IDR. Within this time interval, the curve is fitted with a line to evaluate the intrinsic dissolution rate. The corresponding IDR values are reported in Table 3.

As can be seen in Fig. 5, PVP samples behave the same after preparation using both methods, showing a high increase in IDR compared to the physical mixture. On the basis of the data presented so far, we can conclude that both samples are equivalent. On the other hand, HPMC samples show very strong differences in IDR measurement. The sample from SD performs similarly to the physical mixture, whereas the sample from HME behaves worse with lower IDR even at the beginning of the measurement compared to SD. Such strong dependence of the dissolution profile on the method of preparation of ASD was not expected since

Fig. 3. Solid-state NMR spectra showing used polymer (either PVP K30 (a) or HPMC E5 (b)), crystalline γ and α forms of indomethacin, as well as samples produced by hot-melt extrusion (red) and spray drying (blue).

HPMC was previously used in combination with different production techniques, even though different dissolution behaviour was already shown in the literature for PVP and HPMC for drugs felodipine (Mahmah, 2013) and tadalafil (Huang, 2019).

The possible reason for the poorer performance of the HPMC-containing ASD compared to that of the physical mixture could be the swelling of HPMC polymer. The physical mixture has macroscopic domains of the polymer and drug, while they are molecularly dissolved in the ASD matrix. This could lead to swelling and gelling of the polymer when exposed to the dissolution medium, and the polymer would cover the surface of the IDR disc more thoroughly, limiting the contact of the drug with the medium strongly compared to the poor covering of the disc in the physical mixture case.

3.2. Stress test and following analysis of prepared ASD

Since ASD can suffer from low stability, and to see any possible changes in the physical state of the products, we have performed a stress test at elevated temperature and humidity, i.e., 60 °C and 75 % relative humidity, over a period of 5 days. Macroscopically, there was a visible

difference between the PVP and HPMC samples, where those containing PVP caked together to minimize their volume and so had to be milled before further evaluations by a mortar and pestle. HPMC samples, on the other hand, changed colour, but were still in the powder form (see Fig. 6). For comparison, photos of the freshly prepared sample are shown in Fig. SI 4, where the extruded filaments are shown in the original form, milled extruded powders, as well as spray dried powders. Parallel to visual observation solid-state characterization of the stress-tested samples was performed followed by IDR measurement. After IDR was measured, the samples were again characterized with XRPD and DSC to investigate the propensity to recrystallization of prepared samples due to exposure to both elevated temperature and high humidity for a prolonged time period, followed by immersion of the samples in an aqueous environment for 1 h.

The changes in solid state after the stress test were characterized with solid-state NMR and XRPD measurements. Solid-state NMR data shown in Fig. 7 confirmed that recrystallization occurred, where the SD sample containing PVP recrystallized to the α form of indomethacin, while the HME sample containing PVP did not change from the amorphous form. The SD sample containing HPMC recrystallized to the α form of

Fig. 4. SEM of spray dried powders Ind:PVP (a) and Ind:HPMC (b) and of hot-melt extruded particles of Ind:PVP (c) and Ind:HPMC (d).

Fig. 5. Intrinsic dissolution rates for prepared samples from SD, HME and a comparison to a physical mixture. While the PVP (a)) product seems to have almost no difference between the SD and HME samples, the HPMC (b)) product has a greatly visible difference, with the SD sample dissolving slower than the PVP products but faster than the physical mixture, and the HME sample dissolves even slower than the physical mixture.

indomethacin, while the HME sample containing HPMC has recrystallized to the γ polymorph of indomethacin. For comparison to the samples, α -indomethacin was then prepared using the method adapted from Kaneniwa (Kaneniwa et al., 1985) and has been used further for to compare against the crystalline γ indomethacin polymorph.

Recrystallization was observed for the prepared samples also using XRPD after the stress test (see Fig. 8). However, comparing to the solid-state NMR, after the recrystallization, mixtures of the stable γ and metastable α indomethacin forms occurred, as opposed to the clearly

one or the other crystalline form identified using NMR. The ratios of γ/α forms differed according to the preparation method. In samples prepared by hot-melt extrusion, we observed recrystallization mainly to a stable γ -indomethacin. The spray-dried samples recrystallized mainly to the metastable α -indomethacin form. Furthermore, the spray-dried samples recrystallized more visibly, as evidenced by the intensity of the XRPD peaks in Fig. 8 in the stresses sample curves. This confirms the superior behaviour of PVP in combination with HME, even after exposure to high temperature and humidity, where the sample has retained

Table 3

Evaluated intrinsic dissolution rates from the dissolution plots between times 0 and 500 s using 8 mm discs with 40 ml of phosphate buffer as the dissolution medium with pH 6.8 and 37 °C stirred at 100 rpm.

Sample	IDR ($\mu\text{g}/(\text{ml}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{min})$)
Ind:PVP Spray dried	13.88 ± 1.39
Ind:PVP Hot-melt extruded	13.61 ± 0.11
Ind:PVP Physical mixture	2.92 ± 0.18
Ind:HPMC Spray dried	7.05 ± 0.87
Ind:HPMC Hot-melt extruded	3.78 ± 0.32
Ind:HPMC Physical mixture	4.06 ± 0.38

its amorphous character.

The measured XRPD diffractograms of stressed samples followed by the IDR measurement are shown in Fig. 9. Measurement was carried out directly using the IDR disc to reduce manipulation with the sample. As can be seen, the same behaviour in recrystallization was also observed after the IDR test, i.e., SD samples recrystallize visibly more compared to HME samples. Furthermore, even after exposure to stress test conditions followed by IDR measurement, the Ind:PVP HME sample exhibits only small crystallinity on the surface of the IDR disc and proves to be

resistant to recrystallization. The XRPD test was done to selectively focus on the surface of the IDR disc in direct contact with the dissolution medium, which was also the surface of the XRPD measurement. It should be noted that after the IDR test, the surface of the measured disc was neither flush with the sample holder nor completely flat, possibly leading to errors in the measurement of the quantity of amorphous or crystalline part. However, since the results show behaviour similar to that of previous samples, they were decided to be a good qualitative indicator of the sample surface. This work has not used XRPD for quantitative analysis of the amorphous or crystalline part, for which modulated DSC was utilized.

Complementing the results obtained from the measurement of XRPD, there was a visible impact of the stress test also on the IDR of the prepared samples. The results of these IDR tests are shown in Fig. SI 5 and the corresponding IDR are reported in Table 4. In the case of samples containing PVP, the IDRs have increased when ASD were prepared by HME (from $13.61 \mu\text{g}/(\text{ml}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{min})$ measured for freshly prepared ASD to $16.53 \mu\text{g}/(\text{ml}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{min})$ after stress test), while a strong reduction was observed for sample prepared by SD (from $13.88 \mu\text{g}/(\text{ml}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{min})$ measured in freshly prepared ASD to $6.21 \mu\text{g}/(\text{ml}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{min})$ measured in the stressed sample). Furthermore, for stressed sample produced by SD

Fig. 6. Images of samples after 5 day stress test at 60 °C and 75 % RH, SD Ind:PVP (A), HME Ind:PVP (B), SD Ind:HPMC (C) and HME Ind:HPMC (D).

Fig. 7. Solid-state NMR spectra showing crystalline γ (black line) and α (magenta) indomethacin forms, as well as changes from the materials as produced to the materials after the stress test. SD samples after preparation are shown in blue, after the stress test in navy, while HME samples after preparation are shown in red, after the stress test in maroon. The vertical lines show the peaks of the appropriate crystalline sample for easier assignment of the recrystallized samples, with black lines corresponding to the γ form and magenta lines to the α form of indomethacin.

Fig. 8. Samples diffractograms obtained after the stress test, coupled with diffractograms of indomethacin γ and α for easier visualization of recrystallization peaks. Samples were spray dried (SD) or hot-melt extruded (HME), prepared with indomethacin stabilized with PVP (Ind:PVP) or HPMC (Ind:HPMC).

Fig. 9. XRPD diffractograms of samples exposed to stress test and subsequent IDR measurement. The XRPD measurement was performed using the IDR measurement disc. For comparison are also shown diffractograms of crystalline γ and α indomethacin. The scale for the crystalline samples is selected to allow the data to fit one plot, while the stressed and IDR measured samples share a common Y axis to allow for comparison of recrystallization magnitude.

the dissolution profile follows almost completely the dissolution curve of crystalline α indomethacin. These results are in line with the XRPD data shown in Fig. 8, as well as with the solid-state NMR data shown in Fig. 7, and clearly confirm different recrystallization paths for HME or SD, with samples produced by HME being more stable against recrystallization.

Both HPMC samples show a decrease in the IDR; the spray-dried sample after stress test dissolves at the beginning with the same rate as the freshly spray dried sample but slows down in time to dissolve even slower than the crystalline products of either form. This could be caused by a better distribution of the HPMC polymer around the drug particles, which, when exposed to the dissolution medium, can produce a gel layer that would retard dissolution. As the crystalline materials are mixed macroscopically, they are likely swelling into a gel in a way that covers only partially the API particles. As for the extruded HPMC sample, the already poor dissolution behaviour of the raw product deteriorates even more after the stress test. These results further confirmed that even after the stress test, HME combined with PVP represents a robust formulation in terms of improving dissolution and stabilization of amorphous indomethacin.

To obtain a measure of recrystallization, we have measured DSC thermograms for both samples containing PVP (see Fig. 10) and HPMC (see Fig. 11). Crystallinity has been evaluated by Eq. (1) using the melting enthalpy of the stable γ polymorph, which has a value of 106 J/g, compared to 97 J/g of the α polymorph (Atef, 2012). Please note that this could lead to a 10 % error in the calculation; however, this accuracy is sufficient for the purposes of this work, as assigning the parts of the

Table 4

Intrinsic dissolution rates between time 0–500 s, melting enthalpies of samples after preparation (polymer and technique in the name), after a stress test (polymer, technique, and stress in the name) and after the stress test and IDR measurement (polymer, technique, stress + IDR in the name), as well as their calculated crystallinities. For comparison, the same values are added for physical mixtures composed of fully crystalline starting materials. For some samples, dual melting enthalpies have been observed, indicating dual polymorph recrystallization; however, for simplicity of crystallinity calculation, as well as due to the similarity of the melting enthalpy value between the γ and the α polymorphs, only the melting enthalpy of the stable γ polymorph has been used. The difference between melting enthalpies of the polymorphs is about 10 %. The physical mixture melting enthalpies are adjusted for samples containing only 70 % drug load.

Sample	IDR ($\mu\text{g}/(\text{mL}\cdot\text{cm}^2\cdot\text{min})$)	$\Delta H_{\text{melt}}(\text{J/g})$	Crystallinity (%)
Ind:PVP SD	13.88 ± 1.39	0	0
Ind:PVP SD stress	6.21 ± 0.01	12.9 [123.3 °C]	17.5
Ind:PVP SD stress + IDR	–	24.7 [112.6 °C]	33.3
Ind:PVP HME	13.61 ± 0.11	0	0
Ind:PVP HME stress	16.53 ± 0.27	0	0
Ind:PVP HME stress + IDR	–	0	0
Ind:PVP PM γ	2.92 ± 0.18	74.2 [161.0 °C]	–
Ind:PVP PM α	4.99 ± 0.46	67.9 [153.0 °C]	–
Ind:HPMC SD	7.05 ± 0.87	0.5 [143.3 °C]	0.7
Ind:HPMC SD stress	6.21 ± 0.22	14.5 [136.5; 153.5 °C]	19.6
Ind:HPMC SD stress + IDR	–	59.3 [147.6 °C]	80.0
Ind:HPMC HME	3.78 ± 0.32	0	0
Ind:HPMC HME stress	1.74 ± 0.08	11.9 [131.7; 146.0 °C]	16.0
Ind:HPMC HME stress + IDR	–	27.4 [144.0 °C]	36.9
Ind:HPMC PM γ	4.06 ± 0.38	74.2 [161.0 °C]	–
Ind:HPMC PM α	4.30 ± 0.02	67.9 [153.0 °C]	–

Fig. 10. Reversing heat mDSC curves for PVP samples, after being prepared (spray dried and extruded), after a stress test (SD Stress and HME Stress) and after a stress test followed by an IDR test (SD Stress IDR and HME Stress IDR). Curves clearly show the existence of melting peaks for spray dried samples after the stress test. The peaks were assigned to the α polymorph on the solid-state NMR results.

enthalpy of melting to each polymorph would also bring error in evaluation. Thus, for simplicity, we have decided to use the value of the stable γ polymorph. For evaluation, the DSC measurement utilizes a sample of the bulk of the dissolution disc, not primarily the surface exposed to the dissolution medium, as is the case in the X-ray diffraction measurement. Therefore, with DSC we do not quantify the crystallinity in the exposed layer only, but also possibly less recrystallized inner layers of the stressed powder pressed into the disc. The results of the crystallinity evaluation are shown in Table 4.

The DSC data confirm recrystallization of the HPMC-containing samples, as well as of the SD PVP sample (Figs. 10 and 11 curves called Ind:(polymer) (method) stress, along with data shown in Table 4).

Fig. 11. Reversing heat mDSC curves for HPMC samples, after being prepared (spray dried and extruded), after a stress test (SD Stress and HME Stress) and after a stress test followed by an IDR test (SD Stress IDR and HME Stress IDR). It is visible that both the spray dried and the hot-melt extruded samples were recrystallizing, the spray dried samples being a mixture of the γ and α polymorphs of indomethacin, while the hot-melt extruded samples were mostly composed of the γ polymorph, based on the results of the solid-state NMR results.

Recrystallization is visible as a growth of the melting enthalpy peak around 130–155 °C, as well as by the decrease of the glass transition step of the heat flow curve. Thus, all the solid-state analytical techniques show recrystallization of most of the samples following the stress test, as well as the stability of the Ind:PVP HME sample.

The thermograms show a change from the fresh amorphous samples to partially recrystallized samples after the stress test. Once a small amount of crystals was present, samples after the stress test followed by the IDR test exhibit an increase in the crystallinity. The change from an amorphous sample to a crystalline sample is visible from both the decrease in change of the heat flow around the T_g and the increase in magnitude of the melting enthalpy peak. The assignment of the crystalline form to the melting peaks was carried out by the relative position of the peaks, which means that the first melting peak was assigned to the α form, while the second was assigned to the γ form of indomethacin (Atef, 2012). This is due to the presence of polymer, which does not allow us to directly assign the melting point to those of two polymorphs of indomethacin. The DSC curves show a large amount of the stable γ indomethacin form in the stressed sample, while the stressed samples followed by the SD measured IDR samples prepared by SD show a greater amount of α indomethacin together with a small amount of γ indomethacin. We explain this behaviour by the different rates of transformation of amorphous indomethacin to the metastable (quicker) and stable (slower) forms. In the stress test itself, a long time (5 days at elevated temperature and humidity) allows partial recrystallization of the amorphous indomethacin to the stable γ form. In the case of samples exposed to stress test followed by IDR measurement, some of the amorphous indomethacin is converted into α indomethacin (that is, the duration of IDR measurement is only 1 h) together with the presence of γ indomethacin. The quantitative evaluation is summarized in Table 4, concluding that the only sample without any partial transformation of ASD into crystalline form after the stress test and the IDR measurement is Ind:PVP HME in the bulk of the sample material.

The detection of the recrystallization of Ind:PVP HME sample using XRPD (Fig. 9), which is not visible using the DSC (Fig. 10), although DSC is more sensitive to crystallinity than XRPD, is most likely due to sample manipulation. While the XRPD data are acquired from the surface directly exposed to the dissolution medium in the IDR test, DSC data are acquired from the bulk of the material. In this way, small amounts of the partially recrystallized surface were mixed with high amounts of the non-recrystallized bulk material. This can also explain the presence of the α indomethacin polymorph in the HME sample, as this can be caused by the kinetics of the transformation explained above, due to the comparatively short duration of the dissolution experiment.

Since the conditions discussed above led to a too strong recrystallization of the samples, with recrystallization clearly visible after 5 days

(shown in Table 4) and large differences in IDR before and after the stress test (shown in Fig. SI 5), more stability tests were carried out under milder conditions, that is 30 and 40 °C and two levels of relative humidity of 75 % (high) and 11 % (low) to study the kinetics of recrystallization according to the storage conditions. Crystallinity has been evaluated as before using Eq. (1).

The results of the stability tests show a difference between spray drying and hot-melt extrusion in that hot-melt extruded samples recrystallized at a much slower rate compared to spray drying (see Fig. 12). This could be explained either by a difference in the final domain size of the product (particles in the case of SD or filament in the case of HME) or the difference is inherent to the preparation method, which would then mean that hot-melt extrusion should be the preferred method of preparing stable amorphous solid dispersions with high drug loading. PVP is more effective in stabilizing the amorphous solid dispersion, showing only a slight recrystallization under conditions of 40 °C and 75 % RH, while HPMC was observed to rapidly recrystallize (see Fig. 12).

The observed increase in crystallinity for SD sample containing HPMC is in line with the reduced IDR after the stress test measured (see Fig. SI 5) and with XRD data shown in Fig. 8. This shows interesting characteristics of the spray dried samples, the great importance of storage and handling conditions, and that the extruded samples are not as strongly affected, more so in the filament form of the extrudate.

3.3. Discussion

Hot-melt extrusion appears to provide products with better long-term physical stability compared to spray drying, which is consistent with previous research (Mahmah, 2013; Agrawal, 2013). It can possibly stem from the different particle sizes achieved with spray drying and hot-melt extrusion, leading to a high difference in surface area, with spray-dried products having orders of magnitude higher surface. This leads to the possibility of a higher recrystallization, as the crystals of glasses grow significantly faster on surfaces (Sun, 2011). However, stability can be an issue for hot-melt extruded products if thermal degradation is an issue; then spray drying should be preferred (Hengsawas Surasarang, 2017). Through a novel scientific view of polymorphism, comparisons between quench cooling, spray drying, and hot-melt extrusion has been carried out (Dedroog et al., 2019). It has been shown that quench cooling could lead to a more stable amorphous product compared to spray drying. In addition, hot-melt extrusion has been shown to be the method capable of producing the highest drug load while also producing an amorphous solid dispersion (Dedroog et al., 2019). It was shown in the literature that hot-melt extruded samples can recrystallize to different polymorphs of a crystalline drug than spray dried samples for miconazole (Guns, 2011), which is also the case for indomethacin, as shown in this study.

When XRPD was used as a characterization technique for recrystallization, we have observed the transformation of amorphous indomethacin predominantly to stable γ form when the HME sample was stress tested, while the SD sample has undergone transformation primarily to metastable α form of indomethacin during the stress test. After a stress and IDR tests, the same crystalline form formed as after just the stress test. The DSC of samples that have undergone a stress test has shown a preference to recrystallize to the stable γ indomethacin form, which after stress and IDR tests was the preferred crystalline form only for recrystallizing HME samples. The recrystallizing SD samples transformed into the metastable α indomethacin form. We explain this behaviour by dissolution of both the amorphous and stable γ indomethacin forms, leading to exposure of new amorphous indomethacin to the dissolution medium and in the short time of the dissolution experiment, as well as due to continuous dissolution of the indomethacin, which transforms it to the metastable α indomethacin form. Thus, we show that there is a combination of dissolution and kinetically controlled transformation of amorphous \rightarrow α indomethacin \rightarrow γ

Fig. 12. Change in crystallinity (evaluated from melting enthalpy) of spray dried (blue) and hot-melt extruded (red) samples under different conditions of stability test. Samples prepared with PVP are shown as circles, and samples prepared with HPMC are shown as triangles. Due to overlapping, some symbols are hidden behind each other at a zero-crystallinity value. The conditions used were 30 °C (a, b) and 40 °C (c, d) and relative humidity of 11 % (a, c) and 75 % (b, d)).

indomethacin, where the second step is time-limited. This is in agreement with the results shown on recrystallization of amorphous indomethacin with an intermediate α indomethacin (Ewing et al., 2014).

Previous research on solid indomethacin and felodipine solutions with PVP or HPMC has shown that HPMC appears to inhibit recrystallization of a supersaturated solution slightly better (by allowing greater supersaturation and for longer time) compared to PVP (Konno, 2008; Mah, 2016). In this work, we have shown that solid solution with PVP is better protected against recrystallization in solid form. This provides an interesting perspective for use in the pharmaceutical industry, since knowledge of the physical stability in both the solid form and the supersaturated solution is of importance and this could give a guideline for how to prepare the product. Based on the results presented in this work, the authors suggest preparing a solid solution of PVP and indomethacin using hot-melt extrusion followed by milling of the filament to a powder and pre-mixing it with HPMC powder extragranularly, as well as additional needed excipients, before a tableting process.

Compared to a study on hydrochlorothiazide or ramipril with a different choice of polymeric stabilizers, where the hot-melt extruded products had higher intrinsic dissolution rates compared to spray dried products (Kelleher, 2018), in this study we have shown that indomethacin dissolves with the same rate (the case of Ind:PVP products) or more slowly after hot-melt extrusion than after spray drying (the case of Ind:HPMC products). The physical stability of the HME products was also higher compared to that of the SD products, which is in contrast to the results obtained in the antihypertensive products (Kelleher, 2018). This should clearly illustrate the need to closely probe each relevant combination of drug-polymer production method as well as the need to advance in the field of *in silico* modelling. Furthermore, any extrapolation using past experiences into new pharmaceutical products should be avoided, at least until more data is gained on the underlying principles of amorphous system production and their recrystallization behaviour.

4. Conclusion

The results show a strong difference between the polymer (PVP K30 or HPMC E5) used on the properties of a solid solution with indomethacin. The behaviour of PVP K30 is independent of the production method resulting in a fivefold increase in IDR, while HPMC E5 almost did not increase IDR and at the same time showed strong differences between the production methods. Furthermore, the hot-melt extruded sample containing PVP K30 has not recrystallised until stress test and subsequently being exposed to the dissolution medium, as evidenced by XRPD and DSC, while the spray dried sample containing PVP K30 recrystallized strongly after the stress test, even more so after exposure to the dissolution medium, and showed a steep decrease in IDR after a stress test. Less recrystallization was also observed in the HPMC E5 case when hot-melt extrusion was used compared to spray dried sample; therefore, we conclude that hot-melt extrusion is a better method to prepare stable indomethacin amorphous solid dispersions. The stability of indomethacin products could most likely be extended even further by adjusting the API:polymer ratio, however, this was outside of the scope of this work.

An interesting property was observed in recrystallization. Depending on the production method, a different crystalline state was predominantly produced. Spray drying led to the production of a mixture of the stable and metastable crystalline forms of indomethacin. The hot-melt extrusion samples recrystallized less and only in the stable γ form of indomethacin.

For both HPMC samples and the spray dried PVP sample, there was a steep decrease in IDR after a stress test, which corresponds to a higher recrystallization of those samples compared to the extruded PVP sample. The extruded PVP sample had almost no difference in IDR after exposure to elevated temperatures along with non-recrystallization.

In summary, indomethacin is well stabilized by PVP K30 to produce amorphous solid dispersion, with hot-melt extrusion proving to be leading to more stable products with increased dissolution rate compared to the crystalline state in the physical mixture.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dominik Martynek: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Luděk Ridvan:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Mia Sivén:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Šoós:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2025.125331>.

Data availability

Data are available on ZENODO repository and can be found using the name *Stability and recrystallization of amorphous solid dispersions prepared by hot-melt extrusion and spray drying - experimental data* or using the DOI link at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14846712>.

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